

The Social View of Studying female Students in Colleges and Institutes of Physical Education and Sport sciences

from the Point of View of Administrators Working in Selected Universities in the Arab World (a comparative international study)

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This study aimed to identify the social view of the study of female students in the faculties and institutes of physical education and sport sciences in the Arab world, specifically in the countries of (Jordan, Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, and Lebanon). The study sample reached (493) individuals, including (151) males and (342) females from the administrators working as following (132) from the Hashemite University / Jordan, (133) from the University of Jendouba / Tunisia, (138) from Princess Noura University / Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and (90) from the Holy Spirit University / Lebanon). The researchers used the descriptive approach, where the questionnaire was used as a tool to obtain the study data. The results indicated that the social view of the study of female

students in general was (high) and there are differences in the social view between countries in the field of research in favor of Jordan, as well as the results of the study indicated that there are statistical differences according to the gender variable in the fields (health and psychological) in favor of females, while the results indicated that there are no differences in the fields (social and economic). The researchers recommend circulating the results of this study to benefit from them in knowing the social view of the study of female students in colleges and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world.

Keywords: Social View, Students, Physical Education, Arab World, Women.

1. Introduction

Women are considered half of society and one of its basic components and the reason for its survival and continuity as a result of the multiple roles they play, and these roles vary from one society to another, and from one period of time to another, depending on the social pattern prevailing in each society, and with the transformations that the world has witnessed at all levels: political, social, economic and intellectual, and after the end of the industrial revolution, which had a great impact on women's exit to work and obtaining most of their political and social rights, the perception of women and their status changed.

It became involved with men in all fields, which contributed to opening up multiple fields for them, the most important of which is their right to education and work, and even more so they were able to break into areas that were not long ago the preserve of men but not women, perhaps the most prominent and controversial of which is work in the fields of physical education and sports (Fallahi, 2010).

Through the researchers' access to the theoretical literature related to the history of women's participation in the field of sports, they have noticed that some societies not only deprived women of participating in sports programs and practice, but even deprived them of the right to watch sports events, and perhaps one of the most common stories on this subject is the story of the Romanian woman who was prevented from attending a match for her son, but she disguised herself as men and entered the stadium to watch her son's match, and after winning the match, his mother encouraged him remarkably, This exposed her and revealed her secret and strict laws were applied to her because she is a woman, and women in their traditions and customs are even forbidden from watching sports events and tournaments (Al-Sharman et al., 2022) (Hamza and Khoja, 2016).

Many researchers have dealt with various areas in women's lives, including the sports field, where women have practiced sports activity and engaged in various sports for many years, and began to compete with men in

various fields, whether in training, arbitration or play (Khanfar, 2010).

Kamal El-Din and Mubarak (2017) believe that women's participation in sports programs is one of the manifestations of civilizational progress and development in societies, as it is a right for women, because of its positive effects on public health, physical and psychological fitness and the consequent great benefits on the family and society alike through the active role played by women and their involvement in society and their acceptance in it, as women's participation in the sports field is one of the most important developments. Modern during recent decades considering the practice of sports One of the lifestyles followed by many people (Jaballah, 2015).

The faculties of physical education and their various institutes are among the educational institutions that provide physical education and sports sciences to their affiliates and qualify them to engage in the labor market in the field of teaching, training or others, and their services are not limited to males only, but females can also join the faculties of physical education and sports sciences to benefit from them and to play their role in transferring these sciences and knowledge to subsequent generations of both sexes (Adwan, 2021).

The researchers believe that there is a difference in views towards the study of female students and their enrollment in the disciplines of physical education and sciences, due to many differences in the cultures that govern those societies and their religious, social, educational and health values, in addition to the prevailing customs and traditions, some Eastern societies look at the participation of women in the field of sports uncivilized view incompatible with values, customs and religion, unlike other Arab societies whose citizens see that women's study of the disciplines of physical education and sports sciences and work in its various fields is very advisable and natural

Study problem :

Through the researchers' access to the theoretical literature related to the subject of the current study, and since the researchers are specialized and working in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in Arab universities, and due to the scarcity of regional and Arab comparative studies for the enrollment of female students in the study of one of the disciplines of physical education according to the knowledge of the researchers, they have generated a firm desire to explore the depths of this field and carry out the current study to highlight the social view of the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes In the Arab world from the point of view of administrators working in universities in Jordan, Tunisia, Lebanon and Saudi Arabia.

The problem of the study lies in identifying the social view of the students' study of any of the disciplines of physical education and sports

sciences from the point of view of administrators working in Arab universities in order to promote and strengthen the positive social view and change the non-positive social view and replace it with a positive optimistic view for the general leading role played by women studying physical education disciplines in the prevention of movement deficiency diseases .And inactivity and improving physical, health and psychological fitness among different segments of society and thus achieving the principle of healthy citizenship and the modern civil state.

Objectives of the study :

Identify the social view for the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world in selected universities from (Jordan, Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, and Lebanon) in general .

Identify the differences in the social view of the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world according to the variable of the country, including (Jordan, Tunisia, Lebanon, and Saudi Arabia).

Identify the differences in the social view of the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world according to the variables of the study (gender, academic qualification, social relationship with the study (sister / daughter) for all members of the study sample.

Study Questions:

What is the social view for female students' studies in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world?

Are there differences in the social view of female students' studies in colleges and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world according to the country variable?

Are there differences in the social view of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world according to the variables of the study (gender, academic qualification, years of service, social relationship with the study (sister / daughter)?

Importance of the study :

Identify the view of Arab societies for students' study of physical education disciplines and thus strengthen this view if it is positive and try to change it if it is not positive.

Studying the views of different Arab societies to study the disciplines of physical education and sports sciences increases the societal culture and exposure to the different cultures of the countries participating in the study.

Improving the programs offered to female students in the disciplines of physical education to improve the society's view of these disciplines.

Providing the Arab library with comparative Arab studies in one of the vital aspects in the lives of individuals, which is the study of physical education and sports sciences by women and its reflection on the state and individuals.

Limitations of the study :

Spatial boundaries: The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, the Republic of Tunisia, the Republic of Lebanon, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia .

Time limits: This study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Human Limits: A random sample of administrators working in (Hashemite University / Jordan, Noura Bint Abdul Rahman University / Saudi Arabia, University of Jendouba / Tunisia, and Holy Spirit University / Lebanon) was selected.

2. Method and Procedures

Research Methodology:

The researchers used the descriptive approach in the style of survey studies by designing a questionnaire to find out the social view of the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world from the point of view of administrators working in the universities and institutes concerned to appropriate this approach to the nature of the study and its objectives.

Study population and sample:

Community: All administrators working in the concerned universities in Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, and Lebanon.

Sample: The study sample was randomly selected and numbered (493) individuals distributed as follows (133) from the Hashemite University / Jordan, (133) from the University of Jendouba / Tunisia and (138) from Princess Nourah bint Abdul Rahman University / Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Table (1) indicates the distribution of the sample members on the variables of the study.

Table 1. Distribution of Study Sample Members According to Study Variables

Variable	Level	Number	Percentage
Country	Jordan	132	26.77
	Saudi Arabia	138	27.99
	Lebanon	90	18.25
	Tunisia	133	26.97
Gender	male	151	30.62
	Female	342	69.37
Qualification	High school	68	13.79
	diploma	47	9.53
	Bachelor	253	51.31
	Graduate	125	25.35
Years of service	Less than 3 years	64	12.98
	3 – 5 years	60	12.17
	More than 5 years	369	74.84
Sister/daughter	Yes	123	24.94
	No	370	75.05
studying physical education	493		%100

Study Tool:

Through the researchers' access to the theoretical literature related to the subject of the study, they have designed a tool for the study consisting of (30) phrases, they presented it to specialists in the field of education and sports, and after the tool was retrieved from the arbitrators, the required amendments were made, and the response was according to the five-point Likert scale, where the tool was adopted in its final form consisting of (24) items distributed on the following areas (health dimension, psychological dimension, social dimension, economic dimension)

Tool stability: To verify the stability of the instrument, the internal consistency of the scale was applied using the Cronbach-alpha equation and the results were as in Table .(2)

Table 2. Stability Coefficients Using Cronbach Alpha

Domain	Number of vertebrae	Stability coefficient (Cronbach alpha)
Health	3	0.74
Psychological	5	0.82
Social	11	0.89
Economic	5	0.72
Total	24	0.90

It is clear through the presentation of Table (2) that the stability

coefficient on the health field was (0.74) and on the psychological field (0.82) and on the economic field (0.72) and finally the social field was the stability coefficient (0.89) while the stability coefficient on the fields of study in general came with a degree of (0.90), which is an acceptable value indicating the stability of the paragraphs of the scale in the individual fields and the scale as a whole.

3. Results of the Study

The results related to the first question: What is the social view of the study of female students in the faculties and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world from the point of view of administrators working in the universities concerned.

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages, and standard deviations of the responses of the sample members were calculated as shown in Tables:(3)

Tables 3. Arithmetic Averages, Standard Deviations and Degree of Approval for Study Variables

Variable	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Approval score
Health	4.38	0.57	High
Psychological	4.19	0.59	High
Social	4.08	0.57	High
Economic	3.60	0.63	Medium
Total	4.04	0.46	High

Regarding individual domains:

The first area: health: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of all paragraphs of the field were calculated, as shown in Table:(4)

Table 4. Arithmetic Averages, Standard Deviations and Degree of Approval for Health Domain Items

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Approval Score
1	The study of physical education for female students contributes to the acquisition of moderate strength	4.33	0.75	High
2	The study of physical education for female students increases the body's immunity and ability to resist diseases	4.34	0.70	High
3	Studying physical education for female students a contemporary and healthy lifestyle	4.47	0.66	High
Total		4.38	0.57	High

The second area: psychological: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of all paragraphs of the field were calculated, as shown in Table:(5)

Table 5. Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and degree of agreement for psychological domain paragraphs

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Approval Score
1	Studying physical education for female students increases women's self-confidence	4.37	0.96	High
2	Studying physical education for female students helps relieve psychological anxiety and stress	4.42	0.69	High
3	Studying physical education for female students improves women's self-concept	4.27	0.77	High
4	The study of physical education for female students contributes to satisfying the basic needs of women	3.93	0.82	High
5	Studying physical education for female students helps achieve psychological and emotional balance for women	3.97	0.86	High
Total		4.19	0.59	High

The third area: social: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of all paragraphs of the field were calculated, as shown in Table:(6)

Table 6. Arithmetic Averages, Standard Deviations and Degree of Approval for Social Area Paragraphs

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Approval Score
1	Studying physical education for female students makes them new friends	4.20	0.76	High
2	The study of physical education for female students is gained by culture and various information	4.19	0.73	High
3	The study of physical education for female students contributes to the acquisition of daily life skills	3.95	0.86	High
4	Studying physical education for female students does not conflict with religion and societal customs	4.06	0.89	High
5	Studying physical education for female students is socially acceptable	3.97	0.83	High
6	The study of physical education for female students contributes to women's involvement in society	4.11	0.78	High
7	The study of physical education for female students is a healthy social phenomenon	4.25	0.73	High
8	The study of physical education for female students	4.02	0.98	High

	students is a necessity for advancement and soci urbanization			
9	Studying physical education for female students a woman's right	4.00	0.91	High
10	The study of physical education for fema students is a phenomenon that deserves respect	4.16	0.79	High
11	Studying physical education for female students a solution to many problems in society	3.93	.09	High
Total		4.08	0.57	High

Fourth Area: Economic: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of all paragraphs of the field have been calculated, as shown in Table:(7)

Table 7. Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and degree of agreement for economic field paragraphs

No	Paragraph	Arithme ic Mean	Standard Deviation	Approval Score
1	Studying physical education for female studen increases family income	3.87	0.86	High
2	Studying physical education for female students help empower women	3.21	1.32	Low
3	Studying physical education for female students help keep pace with the requirements and burdens o financial life	3.81	0.82	High
4	The study of physical education for female students an important factor of economic development	3.35	1.14	Medium
5	Studying physical education for female students help achieve financial stability	3.76	0.90	High
Total		3.60	0.63	low

The results related to the second question: Are there differences in the social view of the study of female students in colleges and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world from the point of view of administrators working in universities in countries (Jordan, Tunisia, Lebanon, and Saudi Arabia).

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages, and standard deviations of the responses of the sample members were calculated. This is as shown in tables 8-13:

Table 8. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to the variable of the country (Jordan).

Variable	Arithmetic averages	standard deviations
Health	4.49	0.49
Psychological	4.37	0.45

Social	4.20	0.48
Economic	3.57	0.41
Total	4.14	0.33

Table 9. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to the variable of the country (Saudi Arabia).

Variable	Arithmetic averages	standard deviations
Health	4.27	0.59
Psychological	4.13	0.62
Social	3.69	0.64
Economic	3.51	0.42
Total	3.94	0.46

Table 10. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to the variable of the country (Lebanon).

Variable	Arithmetic averages	standard deviations
Health	4.38	0.59
Psychological	4.22	0.63
Social	4.08	0.56
Economic	4.05	0.70
Total	4.12	0.50

Table 11. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to the variable of the country (Tunisia).

Variable	Arithmetic averages	standard deviations
Health	4.41	0.61
Psychological	4.12	0.57
Social	4.12	0.50
Economic	3.49	0.82
Total	4.02	0.47

To find out the significance of the differences in the averages according to the country variable (Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Lebanon, and Tunisia), a variance analysis test (ANOVA) was performed.

Table 12. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to the country variable (Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Lebanon, and Tunisia).

Domain	Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of squares	Value of F	Level of significance
Health	Between groups	3.43	4	0.85	2.60	0.03
	Inside groups	185.27	561	0.33		
	Total	1.88.70	565			
Psychological	Between	6.12	4	1.53	4.49	0.00

	groups					
	Inside	190.95	561	0.34		
	groups					
	Total	197.07	565			
Social	Between	4.48	4	1.12	3.43	0.00
	groups					
	Inside	188.99	561	0.23		
	groups					
	Total	187.47	565			
	Between	22.58	4	5.64	15.41	0.00
	groups					
Economic	Inside	205.48	561	0.36		
	groups					
	Total	282.07	565			
Total	Between	4.12	4	1.03	4.83	0.00
	groups					
	Inside	119.74	561	0.21		
	groups					
	Total	123.86	565			

The results related to the third question: Are there differences in the social view of the study of female students in the faculties of physical education and sports sciences and their institutes in the Arab world according to the variables of the study (gender, academic qualification, years of service, social relationship with the study (sister / daughter)

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages, and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample were calculated. This is as shown in Tables 13-20:

Table 13. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members according to the gender variable.

	Domain	Health	Psychological	Social	Economic	Total
Male	Arithmetic averages	4.28	4.11	4.01	3.52	3.96
	standard deviations	0.63	0.56	0.59	0.67	0.47
Female	Arithmetic averages	4.42	4.23	4.11	3.63	4.07
	standard deviations	0.54	0.59	0.56	0.61	0.46
Total	Arithmetic averages	4.38	4.19	4.08	3.60	4.04
	standard deviations	0.57	0.59	0.57	0.63	0.46

It is noted through the presentation of the previous table that there are

apparent differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education and to find out the significance of the differences, the researchers conducted the T-test as in the following table:

Table 14. Results of the analysis of the T-test to indicate the differences in the social view of female students in colleges and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world according to the study variable (gender)

Domain	Value (f)	Degrees of freedom	Value (t)	Level of significance
Health	1.95	564	2.59	0.01
Psychological	0.73	564	2.19	0.02
Social	0.55	564	1.86	0.06
Economic	0.79	564	1.82	0.08
Total	0.50	564	2.51	0.01

Table 15. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members according to the variable of academic qualification.

Domain	Health	Psychological	Social	Economic	Total	
High school	Arithmetic averages	4.42	4.22	4.14	3.71	4.10
	standard deviations	0.84	0.58	0.50	0.68	0.44
diploma	Arithmetic averages	4.33	4.14	4.10	3.42	3.99
	standard deviations	0.50	0.43	0.42	0.60	0.33
Bachelor	Arithmetic averages	4.34	4.14	3.99	3.56	3.98
	standard deviations	0.60	0.59	0.58	0.63	0.48
Graduate	Arithmetic averages	4.46	4.30	4.19	3.69	4.14
	standard deviations	0.58	0.61	0.60	0.60	0.47
Total	Arithmetic averages	4.38	4.19	4.08	3.60	4.04
	standard deviations	0.57	0.59	0.57	0.63	0.46

It is noted through the presentation of the previous table that there are apparent differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the variable of scientific qualification and to find out the significance of the differences, the researchers conducted a single variance analysis test (ANOVA) as shown in Table(16)

Table 16. Analysis of the single variance according to the variable of academic qualification.

Domain	Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of squares	Value of f	Level of significance
Health	Between groups	1.77	3	0.59	1.78	0.14
	Inside groups	186.92	562	0.33		
	Total	188.70	565			
Psychological	Between groups	2.73	3	0.91	2.63	0.04
	Inside groups	194.341	562	0.34		
	Total	197.07	565			
Social	Between groups	4.32	3	1.44	4.42	0.00
	Inside groups	183.15	562	0.32		
	Total	187.47	565			
Economic	Between groups	4.22	3	1.40	3.53	0.01
	Inside groups	223.84	562	0.39		
	Total	228.07	565			
Total	Between groups	3.15	3	1.05	4.88	0.00
	Inside groups	120.71	562	0.21		
	Total	123.86	565			

Table 17. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members according to the variable of years of service.

Domain	Health	Psychological	Social	Economic	Total	
Less than 3 years	Arithmetic averages	4.34	4.38	4.12	3.59	4.09
	standard deviations	0.56	0.48	0.48	0.52	0.35
3 – 5 years	Arithmetic averages	4.41	4.21	4.17	3.71	4.11
	standard deviations	0.57	0.57	0.53	0.47	0.38
More than 5 years	Arithmetic averages	4.38	4.16	4.05	3.58	4.02
	standard deviations	0.58	0.60	0.59	0.67	0.49
Total	Arithmetic averages	4.38	4.19	4.08	3.60	4.04
	standard deviations	0.57	0.59	0.57	0.63	0.46

It is noted through the presentation of the previous table that there are apparent differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring

in physical education according to the variable of years of experience and to find out the significance of the differences, the researchers conducted a single variance analysis test (ANOVA) as shown in Table:(18)

Table 18. Analysis of the single variance according to the variable of years of service.

Domain	Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of squares	Value of f	Level of significance
Health	Between groups	0.17	2	0.08	0.26	0.76
	Inside groups	188.53	563	0.33		
	Total	188.70	565			
Psychological	Between groups	2.81	2	1.40	4.07	0.01
	Inside groups	194.26	563	0.34		
	Total	194.07	565			
Social	Between groups	0.92	2	0.46	1.40	0.24
	Inside groups	186.54	563	0.33		
	Total	187.47	565			
Economic	Between groups	1.01	2	0.50	1.25	0.28
	Inside groups	227.05	563	0.40		
	Total	228.07	565			
Total	Between groups	0.71	2	0.35	1.63	0.19
	Inside groups	123.14	563	1.67		
	Total	123.86	565			

Table 19. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations according to your kinship variable (sister / daughter) studying physical education.

Domain	Health	Psychological	Social	Economic	Total	
Yes	Arithmetic averages	4.48	4.39	4.24	3.54	4.15
	standard deviations	0.54	0.50	0.54	0.73	0.45
No	Arithmetic averages	4.35	4.13	4.03	3.62	4.00
	standard deviations	0.58	0.60	0.57	0.60	4.68

It is noted through the presentation of the previous table that there are apparent differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the variable of kinship, and to find out the significance of the differences, the researchers conducted the T-test as shown in Table:(20)

Table 20. Results of the T-test Analysis According to the Kinship Variable Do you have a (sister / daughter) studying physical education.

Domain	Value (f)	degrees of freedom	Value (t)	Level of significance
Health	0.01	564	2.31	0.02
Psychological	4.51	564	4.43	0.00
Social	0.33	564	3.70	0.00
Economic	7.97	564	1.24	0.21
Total	0.06	564	3.24	0.00

4. Discussion of Results

The researchers believe, after what was shown by the results of the statistical analysis in Table (3), that the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education in general is high, as the arithmetic average of the responses of the members of the study sample was (4.04) with a standard deviation of (0.46) on the total scale .

The researchers attribute this result to the fact that the administrators working in the selected universities are characterized by high awareness and an open civilized mentality in their view of studying sports science disciplines by female students, and it is not surprising that the administrators' view is positive, since most of them have bachelor's degrees or higher and work in high-end educational institutions, and this is consistent with what Al-Khalidi and Al-Ruwaili (2021) said.

It is clear from Table (4) that the researchers attribute the occurrence of paragraph (3): The study of physical education for female students is a contemporary and healthy lifestyle on the highest arithmetic average to the fact that the members of the study sample of the educated and educated segment, which believes that the practice of sports activity has become a contemporary and healthy lifestyle in order to achieve physical fitness and avoid diseases of lack of movement and associated symptoms.

Also, the occurrence of paragraph (1): the study of physical education for students contribute to the acquisition of moderate strength on the degree of approval high in the health field researchers believe that this is a logical result so that the practice of sports activity works to maintain moderate strength and avoid distortions, and if any, sport is one of the most effective methods and means to maintain moderate strength.

Referring to Table (5), the researchers attribute the occurrence of paragraph (2): The study of physical education for female students helps in reducing psychological anxiety and tension on the highest arithmetic average to the fact that practicing sports activity is one of the best means used to alleviate psychological stress and introduce happiness and pleasure to the same practitioner, as indicated by many studies to that. As for the occurrence of paragraph (4): the study of physical education for female students contributes to satisfying the basic needs of women. With the lowest arithmetic average in the health field and a high approval score, the researchers believe that this is a logical result so that the practice of sports activity meets the basic needs of the individual, whether physical, psychological, social or emotional, and helps to enjoy a normal life free from psychological pressure and health problems. This has been confirmed (Sindik, et all, 2016).

As for Table (6), the researchers attribute the occurrence of paragraph (7): The study of physical education for female students is a healthy social phenomenon on the highest arithmetic average to the fact that sports activity is one of the most important means of forming new friendships and strengthening old friendships, and the practice of physical activities is one of the means and methods that develop the social aspect of practitioners, whether through group or individual games or even walking or other colors of different sports activity , Paragraph (11): Studying physical education for female students is a solution to many problems in society. At least an arithmetic average in the health field and with a high degree of approval, the researchers believe that this is a logical result so that the study of any of the disciplines of sports and playing various games helps in solving many of the problems of society such as leisure time, diseases of lack of movement, behavioral deviations in young people and psychological problems ,Therefore, the practice of sports activities works to stabilize societies, especially from social diseases, achieve health, stay away from inactivity diseases, and thus achieve good citizenship and the safety of individuals and communities.

Referring to Table (7), the researchers attribute the occurrence of paragraph (1): The study of physical education for female students increases the family income on the highest arithmetic average to the fact that graduates of the specialization of physical education have job opportunities in many and varied fields and the need is always for holders of physical education specialization such as schools, universities, army, security and federations, in addition to clubs, youth centers, fitness centers, as well as various educational and educational institutions, which are characterized by paying fairly high monthly wages .This helps in increasing family income and economic empowerment of workers and their families. Paragraph (2): Studying physical education for female students helps in empowering women. At least an arithmetic average in the health field and a high degree of approval, the researchers believe that this is

a logical result so that working in the fields available to graduates of one of the disciplines of physical education and sports sciences and the monthly salaries they receive enable women in their families and society and become economically independent from their husband or father by securing their various needs without relying on others And secure a decent life for her.

The results of tables (12) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) according to the country variable (Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Lebanon and Tunisia) according to the value and value of (F) calculated in the table, and by referring to the arithmetic averages, we find that the differences in statistical significance were in favor of the State of Jordan, where the researchers believe that the existence of statistically significant differences attributed to the state variable is a logical result, due to the conditions of the state of customs, traditions and values in general, which was reflected in the results of the current study.

Through Table (14), the researchers note that there are no statistically significant differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the gender variable in the fields (social and economic), while the results of the study indicated that there are differences in the social view in the areas of (health and psychological) in favor of females, and from the point of view of the researchers, the females who have been applied to the questionnaire believe that the students' study of the disciplines of physical education and sports sciences helps them achieve psychological and health balance .In terms of having a graceful body free of defects, deformities, and diseases of the age and away from psychological pressures and emotional and emotional problems. It is the most important for women, not economic empowerment, obtaining monthly salaries or establishing social relations, because achieving economic empowerment and female support in our Arab societies is the responsibility of men, and many females are limited to managing family affairs and housewives and enjoying a safe economic life by securing the man, so whether he is a husband, father or brother Also, the social field from the point of view of women (females) can be achieved through family relations, whether a small family or an extended family through relatives or girlfriends and daughters of neighbors and the neighborhood where the students live, and therefore the social and economic field can be provided through families while the health and psychological fields need other sources to secure them and that one of these sources is the study of physical education and sports sciences in universities and various scientific institutes, and this is what was pointed out by (Mirsafian & Dosze, 2013).

The researchers have noticed through the presentation of Table (16) the existence of statistically significant differences in the social view for the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the variable of scientific qualification in the fields (psychological, social and economic) in

favor of postgraduate studies, while the results of the study indicated that there are no differences in the social view in the field (health), and from the point of view of the researchers, the administrators working in the universities of the study sample of postgraduate holders (Master and PhD) They believe that studying one of the disciplines of physical education and sports sciences achieves psychological, social and economic security for students studying physical education, while the health field there are no differences between parents who have higher degrees, and perhaps the reason is that those with higher scientific degrees have a more profound view, analysis, awareness and knowledge by virtue of their studies and provide them with the opportunity to see and know more than other scientific degrees.

Also, through the presentation of Table (18), the researchers note that there are statistically significant differences in the social view for the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the variable of years of experience in the field (psychological) and in favor of the years from 3-5 years, while the results of the study indicated that there are no differences in the social view in the areas of (health, social and economic), and from the point of view of researchers, administrators with experience of (3-5) years believe that the study of female students for the specialization of physical education achieves psychological safety for them compared to With less or more years of experience Perhaps because the experience of (3-5) years is moderate and balanced experience in judging things, while less experience may be not mature enough to judge things, as well as perhaps more experience may be more analytical and deep that sports activity achieves various psychological, social, health and economic aspects.

Finally, by presenting Table (20), the researchers note that there are statistically significant differences in the social view of the study of female students majoring in physical education according to the variable of kinship Do you have a (sister / daughter) studying physical education in the fields (health, psychological and social) in favor of There is no (sister / daughter) studying physical education, while the results of the study indicated that there are no differences in the social view in the field (economic) and from the point of view of researchers, they believe that administrators working in universities under study who do not have (sister or daughter) There are no statistical differences, considering that the matter of spending and achieving economic security It is the responsibility of the man, whether he is a father, brother or husband, as part of our Islamic and religious faith, while researchers believe that there are statistically significant differences in other areas (psychological, social and health) because of the positive effects and good repercussions of female students studying for one of the disciplines of physical education.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

- The social view of female students' study of physical education was high in general and for all variables of study.
- The social view of female students' study of physical education was low in the economic field.
- There are differences according to the country variable, and in favor of the State of Jordan. And in gender variable in the two fields (health and psychological) and in favor of females. And in scientific qualification in the fields (social, psychological, and economic) and in favor of postgraduate studies. And in years of experience in the field (psychological) and in favor of the years of 3-5 years. And in specialization of physical education according to the variable of kinship in the fields (psychological, health and social) and in favor of there is no (sister / daughter) studying physical education.
- there are no differences in the social view of female students' study of physical education according to the gender variable in the two fields (social and economic). (scientific qualification), (years of service). (kinship variable),

The researchers recommend circulating the results of this study to benefit from them in knowing the social view of the study of female students in colleges and institutes of physical education and sports sciences in the Arab world, and the researchers recommend conducting studies like this study dealing with all Arab countries, and perhaps expanding the circle to include Arab and non-Arab countries.

References

- Adwan, Nimr, (2021). Awareness of nanotechnology and its mathematical applications among faculty members in faculties and departments of physical education in Palestine, unpublished master's thesis. An-Najah National University,
- Ansari, Mona. (2002). Attitudes towards physical activity among women in the State of Bahrain. *Journal of Sports Sciences and Arts*, Vol. 16(2): 1-25.
- Battikhi, Nihad and Hassouna, Osama. (2012). The role of the administration of the Faculty of Physical Education at the University of Jordan in encouraging women's sports and reducing the challenges and obstacles facing students from the point of view of the students themselves. *Journal of Educational Sciences Studies*. 2(43): 563 – 577.
- Bou Saleh, Kazem. (2003). Women's attitudes towards the importance of practicing sports activity for female students at King Faisal University in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Science*, 4(1): 104-122.
- Fallahi, Karima. (2010). Manifestations of social values among women practicing physical exercise. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. Vol. 1(22): 57-82.
- Jaballah, Zahia. (2015). Women's sports are a health necessity or a culture and health awareness. *Hikma Journal of Social Studies*. 3(6): 124 – 135.

- Hamza, Ghadban and Khoja, Bassem and Shalabi, Walid. (2016). The reality of women's sports practice and the attitudes of Algerian girls towards it. A Field Study, *Al-Tahadi Journal*, 16(1):169-181.
- Kattan, Samia. Najjar, Enaam and Khalifa, Hessa and Jaafar, Hussein. (2015). Women's Sports in the Kingdom of Bahrain: Reality, Challenges and Aspirations. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences*. Vol. 16(3): 13–62.
- Kamal El-Din, Hazem and Mubarak, Hossam El-Din. (2017). Administrative planning for employees of the Women and Girls Center at the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Dakahlia Governorate. *Journal of the Faculty of Physical Education*, Vol. 1(29): 403-421.
- Khalidi Bashayer and Ruwaili, Asma. (2021). Social factors associated with Saudi women's awareness of physical exercise: a field study on female participants in sports clubs, *Saudi Journal of Social Studies*. 1(8): 33 – 66.
- Khanfar Waleed. (2010). Obstacles to Playing Football among Physical Education Students in Palestinian Universities *An-Najah University Journal for Research (Humanities)*, Vol. 24(6):1-17.
- Mirsafian, H., Dosze, T., (2013). Attitude of Iranian female university students to sport and exercise. *Iranian studies* 47(1): 951 – 966.
- Shorman, Abdel Basset & Tahaina, Ziad & Khasawneh, Aman & Haliq, Mahmoud & Hatamleh, Mahmoud & Khalidi, Hassan & Harafasha, Ibrahim & Sharman, Salwa & Khuraisat, Raee & Hamad, Amal. (2023). *Physical Culture*. The Hashemite University, College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences, The Hashemite University. Dar Scheherazade. Amman.
- Sindik, J., Dodigovic, L., Mikic, Z., Corak, S., (2016). Analyses of the relevant factors for the engaging women in various sports in Croatia. *Montenegrin journal of sport science and medicine* 5(1): 17 – 28.